

Supplementary Table ST2: Taxonomy of AI Tasks in Weather Forecasting

AI Task	Description	Prevalence	Example Studies
Regression / Point Forecasting	Prediction of continuous meteorological variables (temperature, wind speed, rainfall amount)	42.4% (42/99)	S6, S23, S36, S45, S66, S72, S76, S92
Classification	Binary or multi-class prediction of weather events (rain occurrence, fog, convective initiation)	17.2% (17/99)	S2, S4, S20, S29, S30, S55, S70, S87
Spatiotemporal Prediction	Forecasting sequences of gridded fields (radar reflectivity, geopotential height, temperature fields)	14.1% (14/99)	S3, S7, S11, S27, S50, S57, S65, S74, S80,
Post-processing / Bias	Correcting systematic errors in NWP or satellite products	12.1% (12/99)	S9, S17, S25, S26, S33, S37, S39, S51, S61,
Downscaling / Super-	Increasing spatial resolution of coarse meteorological fields	4.0% (4/99)	S9, S10, S11, S48
Ensemble / Probabilistic	Generating uncertainty estimates via multiple predictions	6.1% (6/99)	S1, S10, S21, S64, S71, S93
Attribution / Driver Analysis	Quantifying meteorological drivers of environmental variables	2.0% (2/99)	S13, S28
Parameterization / Emulation	Replacing physical parameterization schemes in climate models	1.0% (1/99)	S83
Information Retrieval / QA	LLM-based retrieval of weather information without forecasting	1.0% (1/99)	S11